

Not only Text and Data but also Software. Modern Research Software Architecture for Legacy DH Projects. Travelogue Portals in Digital History. Showcasing the new digiberichte.de

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Maintaining software projects over a longer period of time is challenging. Not only security fixes have to be applied, but from time to time new features need to be added, or the user interface need to be updated to fit more actual needs. We want to share our experience and strategy for a successful reengineering of legacy websites with “digiberichte.de” as an example. The project started 2007 as a retro-digitization effort of printed analytical bibliographies on late-medieval travelogues and covers bibliographical information about the travelers and their itineraries, mostly originating from the areas corresponding to modern-day Germany, Benelux and France (Halm 2001; Hirschbiegel and Kraack 2000; Wettlaufer and Paviot 1999). Some basic information about travelers from Italy, UK and Russia was added later on. The project website has seen three iterations since the initial release (Wettlaufer 2010). This poster presents the new web application that has been created in 2024 on the bases of the original research data and discuss the approach adopted to carry out the modernization work. The application provides KWIC access to the bibliographic data as well as to the full texts of relevant primary and secondary literature, and visualizes travelers’ itineraries using industry-standard web mapping technologies. Overall, we see “digiberichte.de” as a positive example of evolving RSE practices over the last twenty years, practices that can be applied to other research software projects to improve their usefulness and extend their reach

(Wettlaufer and Paravicini, n.d.). RSE is not limited to writing code. The software production workflow encompasses complementary disciplines such as project coordination, knowledge sharing, issue tracking and resolution and release management. Modern RSE starts with the adoption of modern approaches to these disciplines. In order to implement such approaches, our group has been using the DevSecOps platform GitLab to manage and release our software projects, which acted as scaffolding for the development of microservice-based systems, namely systems that consist of multiple services, each handling a distinct function independently (cf. the seminal publication Dragoni et al. 2017 for a general overview). The services interact with each other using standard protocols such as HTTP, which allows for the use of virtually any language and framework when creating a new service. This loose coupling of components makes it possible for members of the project to work separately on individual services with ease, as long as the interface to other services is well-defined. Of course, it has a series of other technical advantages, too: Single services are isolated and don’t interfere directly with the correct functioning of other services, deployment cycles can happen more frequently on a service-to-service basis and (horizontal) scalability is easier to achieve thanks to the inherent distributedness. Below is a simplified diagram of the current version of “digiberichte.de” following the popular design trichotomy frontend, middleware and backend.

Figure 1: Components of digiberichte.de (as of Version 0.2.1)

The user interface, or frontend, consists of a Vue single-page application with two different search modes: Facet-based search across the bibliographic metadata and full text search across the content of the bibliographic texts. The metadata search uses the popular web mapping library Leaflet to both allow for visual spatial search and represent itineraries on an interactive map. The full text search view shows results as KWICs. The frontend consumes the data produced by a series of services that can thought of as the

“backend” of DigiBerichte, currently being the modolithic Web API and the PDF processing server ARPAD, a standalone project that will be open-sourced soon. The Solr client embedded in the Web API abstracts away the complexity of Solr’s JSON Request API so that data manipulation on the frontend becomes easier, while ARPAD is used to preprocess PDF documents fetched from a WebDAV store, which allows for different kinds of PDF downloads on the frontend. The “storage layer” includes the aforementioned WebDAV store, containing bibliographic texts, a database containing bibliographic metadata, which is a revised and expanded version of the project’s original dataset, and a Solr service for indexing and searching through both of these kinds of data. The map visualization of the travelers’ itineraries is generated dynamically from the data retrieved from Solr and supports particular features such as clustering and automated geocoding error correction. All bibliographic data collected during the project is CC-BY-SA-4.0 and can be reused in other projects. The software underlying “digiberichte.de” has recently been adopted in another project on travelogues called “middle-east-travelers.de”, which is a project on European travelers to the Ottoman Empire in the long 19th century. The workflow arising from the adoption of modern RSE practices and a microservice-based architecture has proven itself to be productive, reproducible and incredibly flexible.

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